

IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF FORMING FEELINGS OF COUNTRY PRIDE AND PRIDE IN THE STUDENTS OF MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *To educate young people in the spirit of military patriotism, to teach them to love their country, people and family, to learn the great legacy of our patriotic grandfathers and to become their worthy heirs.*

Keywords: *patriotism, concept of patriotic person, military patriotism, legal education, legal culture.*

In the **introduction** of the article, the directly relevant issue is that the reforms are spreading more and more widely in our independent Uzbekistan, in which drastic changes are taking place in all aspects of our nation, including the education of the young generation. Actions to restore and further enrich our history, spirituality, fundamental changes in the way of education and personnel training are among these. These things are not done for nothing. Because the development of any country depends on the level of knowledge and spirituality of the people. In this regard, the first President of our country, I.A. Karimov, said the following words: "First of all, the great country of the future should take care of the culture, education and spirituality of its future citizens." The adoption of the Law on Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the National Program of Personnel Training is an indication of this concern. As in every field, great positive changes are taking place in the training of military specialists. Demands on military personnel are increasing. Because today's military serviceman is not only a specialist with limited knowledge in a certain field, but a person with deep intellectual abilities, broad outlook, high culture and spirituality, who with his knowledge and personal example It is necessary to be a pedagogue who can educate and educate his subordinates.

In military servicemen, it is necessary to cultivate the feelings of love for the Motherland, respect for our national values, the rich and great history of our Motherland and pride in it, the sacredness of the family characteristic of our people, respect for elders, love and attention to children. Patriotic education is an integral part of the national ideology, and the issue of educating military personnel in this spirit is one of the main tasks of military education. Military patriotism is a special type and an integral part of national and national patriotism. Military training consists of training in the spirit of loyalty to the country, educating the qualities of humanity and humanity, instilling our national traditions, customs, and feelings into the minds of the soldiers. Reviving the memory of the people's history and awakening their national pride and nobility is one of the most tried and tested ways of realizing the national identity.

It is necessary to develop military service members' feelings of love for the Motherland, unlimited respect for our national values and the rich and great history of our Motherland and pride in it, the sacredness of the family characteristic of our people, respect for elders, love and attention for children. Patriotic education is an integral part of the national ideology, and the issue of educating military personnel in this spirit is one of the main tasks of military education. Military

patriotism is a special type and an integral part of national and national patriotism. Military training consists of training in the spirit of loyalty to the country, educating the qualities of humanity and humanity, instilling our national traditions, customs, and feelings into the minds of the soldiers. Reviving the memory of the people's history and awakening their national pride and nobility is one of the most tried and tested ways of realizing the national identity.

In the conditions of independence, higher military education plays a special role in providing the servicemen with thorough knowledge of our national spirituality and worldly sciences, and instilling the main ideas of the national independence ideology.

Today, there are the main factors of bringing the ideas of national independence to the minds of military personnel:

- Fulfilling civic duties and tasks before the country and nation;
- Formation of high morale among military personnel;
- Cultivating in them the spirit of respect for our spiritual heritage and forming loyalty to the Motherland;
- Education of military personnel in the spirit of military patriotism;
- Formation of moral and aesthetic education in them;
- Gaining respect for the national language, explaining the importance of learning other languages as well.

Teaching and studying the authoritative works of scholars such as Farabi, Al-Bukhari, At-Tirmizi, Sheikh Najmiddin Kubro, Az-Zamakhshari, Bahauddin Naqshband, who help to ensure the spiritual and moral education of military personnel.

It is necessary for us to inherit from our ancestors how to protect the independence of mother Uzbekistan, its honor, and to be always ready to protect it. Let the feeling of love for the Motherland, which is a sacred heritage from our great ancestors, become a true belief and creed for our children, present and future generations. The battle between Jalaluddin Manguberdi, a brave national hero, a great man, a patriot who sacrificed his life for the freedom of the country, and Genghis Khan was so fierce that historians of that time say that other battles were child's play in front of him. It is natural that the means and methods of educating military personnel in the spirit of devotion to duty are unique. We should talk about the public means of educating cadets, listeners, and young military personnel in the spirit of love for the country and devotion to duty, in the perfect mastery of their duties. In educational work, the attention of young people is focused on the heroic past of our people, national traditions of the Uzbek people, great contribution of our people to the world civilization, its centuries-old culture, promotion of our national traditions. One of the important directions of military training is to acquaint the personnel with the changes taking place in the internal and external politics, economy, science, culture and social sphere of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Another important area of military education is the continuation of military traditions in the military sphere. So, in general, in the training of future soldiers in military education, in forming them to love the Motherland, their chosen profession, spare no effort in the way of maintaining the peace and tranquility of the people, the command of the educational institution, the teaching staff, the father - in the cooperation of mothers, we can put the military education at the highest level until taking great measures.

Today, there are the following pedagogical factors for creating a healthy moral environment in the military and instilling the idea of national independence into the minds of military personnel:

Preparation of military personnel to perform civic duties and tasks before the Motherland and the nation from the issues of national consciousness, social, political, economic, and spiritual education based on national and universal values;

Formation of high morale among military personnel, training them in the spirit of overcoming difficulties with initiative, correctly determining the qualities that can meet the requirements of the time, the interests of our motherland, our people;

Cultivating in them the spirit of respect for our spiritual heritage, perfect assimilation of our history, ensuring active participation in the process of restoration of spiritual values;

Conducting various military and civil defense competitions in order to educate military personnel in the spirit of military patriotism and to teach them to respect our national values;

Formation of moral and aesthetic education in military personnel;

Explaining the importance of learning other languages along with raising respect for the national language among military personnel;

Teaching and teaching the respected works of scholars such as Farabi, al-Bukhari, at-Tirmizi, Sheikh Najmiddin Kubro, az-Zamakhshari, Bahauddin Naqshband, who help to ensure the spiritual and moral education of military personnel.

To strive to maintain peace, tranquility and well-being in our country, to understand the development of the eastern traditions of democracy in the conditions of independence of the military, to respect public opinion, to act with long-term thinking, not to give in to passion and emotions, to develop a culture of self-control in any difficult situation. It is necessary to pay great attention to the formation. Development takes place only where peace, harmony, and tranquility are stable, when young people realize that a person can achieve his dreams, which leads to the rise of patriotism to the level of duty and responsibility. As we know, one of the main ideas of the ideology of national independence is the peace of the country. This is not for nothing, because for centuries, our ancestors, at all stages of the development of mankind, first of all, sought peace and harmony, because the peace of the country is the guarantee of stable development.

In **conclusion**, young people are the future of our country and nation. We entrust the fate of our country to them. For this, they should fully understand the most complex and responsible task assigned to them, and contribute to it. Therefore, every serviceman serving in the Armed Forces must be educated in the spirit of high patriotism. Patriotism is a high human virtue. Patriotism is one of the brightest forces of perfection. That is why in the Hadith Sharifs, it is urged that "To love the country is from faith."

It requires a strictly objective approach to the analysis of evidence, process and events and to consider them from all sides. Military patriotism education should be combative, active, able to attack, it should be able to reveal shortcomings in the preparation of the country's youth for the defense of the Motherland and take measures to eliminate them.

In education of military patriotism, the principle of clear-historical approach, which envisages consideration of all real situations as their development and change over time, is of great importance.

This principle presupposes the compatibility of the content, forms and methods of military-patriotic education in the specific historical situation.

The principle of a clear-historical approach is also manifested in military-patriotic work, which is closely related to human education based on the heroic history of the people and the

Armed Forces. Accordingly, objective coverage of historical events without changing the truth is of great importance.

One of the important principles of military patriotism is unity of patriotism and international education. The fact that patriotism and international tasks are organically interconnected and mutually conditioned in the activities of all educators serves as a powerful factor that forms the personality of a fighter, constantly reminds him why he takes up arms and defends.

One of the principles of military patriotism education is embodied in a different approach to different groups of young people. This principle requires that our multi-ethnic state should be built taking into account the interests and characteristics of military patriotism education, customs and national traditions of different nationalities and peoples.

The effectiveness of military patriotism education is carried out through a certain existing system, which includes specific tasks, content, form, method and means, various state and social bodies, organizations and institutions that solve specific specific tasks.

This system has a general feature, that is, formation of patriotism in young people is the task of all higher and secondary special educational institutions of our society.

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